

Secondary Science Teachers' Views about Purposes of Practical Works in School Science

Authors : Kew-Cheol Shim, Sung-Hwan Moon, Ji-Hyon Kil, Kyoungho Kim

Abstract : The purpose of this paper was to examine views of secondary school science teachers about purposes to use practical works in school science. The instrument to survey consisted eighteen items, which were categorized into four components as follows: 'Scientific inquiry', 'Scientific knowledge', 'Science-related attitude', and 'STS (science-technology-society)'. Subjects were 152 secondary school science teachers (male 70 and female 82; middle school 50 and high school 102), who are teaching in 42 schools of 8 provinces. On the survey, science teachers were asked to answer on 5-point Likert scale (from 1 to 5) how they thought of using practical works on purposes with domains of science objectives in school. They had positive views about using practical works for improving scientific inquiry process skills, science-related attitudes, and perceptions about STS literacy, and acquiring scientific knowledge. They would have the most willingness of using practical works for 'Scientific Inquiry' among domains of science objectives in school.

Keywords : secondary school, science teacher, practical work, scientific inquiry, scientific knowledge, scientific attitude, STS

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